

Effects of bottom topography on the currents at Ormen Lange.

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Abstract

The second largest gas field in Norway, Ormen Lange, is located at Storegga 140 km west of Kristiansund. Ormen Lange lies in the continental shelf slope where several slides have created a rough bottom topography. The depth varies between 800 to 1100 m.

A three-dimensional, time split, σ -coordinate model is used to study possible effects from the bottom topography on the currents and the hydrography at Ormen Lange.

Measurements in the area have revealed damped oscillations of the density surfaces after a disturbance. Such disturbance can for instance be created by travelling atmospheric low pressure systems or internal density fronts. Model results based on a smooth bottom topography show similar behaviour but the oscillations are much more harmonic, and they are less damped after the main disturbance. The use of a rougher and more realistic bottom topography seems to damp the oscillations more rapidly, and can introduce a decrease in the period.

When studying processes that are strongly influenced by topographic features, it is therefore important to apply as realistic bottom matrices as possible for a given grid resolution. In most ocean model studies the grid resolution will in the foreseeable future be too coarse to resolve the small scale hills and troughs that may extract energy from the larger scale flow. Hence the parametrization of subgrid-scale processes in the larger scale ocean models are important.

1 Introduction

Ormen Lange is the second largest gas field in Norway and located in the Storegga region approximately 130 km offshore off mid-Norway. The depth varies between 800 and 1100 m. This is the first deep water hydrocarbon project outside the Norwegian shelf.

Ormen Lange is located in the core of several submarine slides. This has made the sea bed covered with high escarpments and local sea mounts. Such extreme topography may generate focusing and blocking effects on currents, and internal waves may be generated by these obstacles. These effects are yet poorly resolved by thermohaline circulation models.

An ongoing data acquisition program in the area has identified several events in which the currents close to the sea bed exhibit peak values in their speed and temperature over a short period of time. Earlier reports (Eliassen et al. 2000) have commented on these events and suggested two plausible explanations for the high current speeds occurring at Ormen Lange. Internal waves that break towards the shelf slope or currents at strong internal density fronts. The most pronounced generation mechanism behind internal wave phenomena in this area is believed to be atmospheric forcing, Vikebø et al. (2001).

Both the rough topography and the high current speed in this area may cause problems for near sea bed installations needed for developing, producing and transporting the gas from the field. It is therefore important to understand the phenomena acting at Ormen Lange before the developing of the gas field begins.

This report will focus on how the model bottom bathymetry affect the model results. Two events (with and without storm) will be simulated with bottom topography interpolated from the ETOPO5 (5 min long and lat) data set including refinement around the Ormen Lange area (Figure 1 a)), and bottom topography interpolated from a smooth 20 km grid resolution model (Figure 1 b)). The boundary conditions are described in Vikebø et al. (2001) and the initial conditions are described in Eldevik et al. (2001) .

Figures of velocity, salinity and temperature 10 and 50 m above sea bed will be presented at the locations indicated in Figure 2. The depths at the locations are given in Table 1.

2 Model

This model study uses the numerical σ -coordinate ocean model of Berntsen (2000). The equations are the continuity equation for an incompressible

(a) Interpolated from ETOPO5.

(b) Interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

Figure 1: Model area given in grid coordinates. The grid size is 4 km. The Ormen Lange area is outlined.

(a) The Ormen Lange area (ETOPO5).

(b) The Ormen Lange area (20 km).

Figure 2: Ormen Lange with the locations OL1-OL5.

Model	OL1	OL2	OL3	OL4	OL5
4 km (ETOPO5)	227.8	615.0	851.8	1191.0	826.2
4 km (20 km $\rightarrow$ 4 km)	308.7	591.2	813.4	1175.1	817.0

Table 1: Depths in meters at stations OL1 to OL5

fluid, the Reynold averaged hydrostatic momentum equations, conservation equations for temperature and salinity and the UNESCO-equation of state. The reader is referred to Berntsen (2000) for further details concerning the governing equations and numerical methods.

The model area covers the south eastern part of the Norwegian Sea basin, (see Figure 1) with 4 km horizontal grid resolution. In the vertical 30 σ -layers are applied and these are distributed according to a formula given in Lynch et al. (1995). Their formula distribute the layers symmetrically about the midpoint in the vertical with a gradually finer resolution towards the surface and the bottom.

The model is run for 240 hours with an internal 3-D time step of 120 s. There are 30 2-D time steps per 3-D step. Initial values of water elevation, velocities, temperature and salinity from Eldevik et al. (2001) are interpolated from 20 km into 4 km grid resolution. These are climatological values that have been spun up over a period of 165 days. The spin up process results sharpens the density gradients in the area.

At the lateral open boundaries a flow relaxation scheme (FRS) is implemented (Martinsen and Engedahl, 1987). The FRS-zones are 7 grid-cells wide. In addition to the initial values for water elevation (η), velocity (u and v), temperature (T) and salinity (S), four tidal constituents (M_2 , S_2 , K_1 , N_2), are used to specify the lateral boundary conditions.

Travelling low pressure systems are important driving mechanisms for the oceanic flow. Martinsen et al. (1979) constructed a model of a cyclone and studied barotropic effects of the moving cyclone. The atmospheric pressure disturbance is described by, following Martinsen et al. (1979),

$$p(x, y, t) = p_0(t)e^{\{-(x-x_0-u_0t)^2+(y-y_0-v_0t)^2\}/R^2} \quad , \quad (1)$$

where $p_0(t)$ is the pressure disturbance at the center of the cyclone, x_0, y_0 the initial position of the center of the pressure disturbance, u_0, v_0 are the x and y components of the propagation velocity and R defines the horizontal extent of the pressure disturbance. Wind velocity components u_g and v_g in x and y directions, respectively, are computed from the gradients in the atmospheric

pressure

$$u_g = -\frac{0.7}{f\rho_a} \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} \quad , \quad (2)$$

$$v_g = \frac{0.7}{f\rho_a} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \quad , \quad (3)$$

where f is the Coriolis parameter and ρ_a the density of the air (1.3 kgm^{-3}).

From the wind velocity, wind stress is computed

$$\tau_x = \rho_a c_D (u_g^2 + v_g^2)^{1/2} u_g \quad , \quad (4)$$

$$\tau_y = \rho_a c_D (u_g^2 + v_g^2)^{1/2} v_g \quad , \quad (5)$$

where c_D is the drag coefficient. In our experiments c_D is chosen to be 3×10^{-3} (cf. Martinsen et al. 1979).

For simulations where low pressures are present, the model is first run for 24 hours with $p_0(t) = 0$. The low pressures are then started at positions $(x_0, y_0) = (-235.65, 372.08)$, given in grid coordinates.

Figure 3: Path of the idealized low pressure. Time i hours after simulation start.

The pressure disturbance $p_0(t)$ is increased linearly over the next 12 hours to -60 hPa and held constant for the remaining simulation periods. The propagation velocities are $u_0 = 8.59 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ and $v_0 = -4.81 \text{ ms}^{-1}$, and the radius is 500 km. See Figure 3.

Four experiments will be performed. Two of them with no low pressure present, and two of them with a relatively strong travelling low pressure. To study the effect of the bottom topography, two different bathymetry sets are used. The first where topography from a 20 km grid resolution model is interpolated into 4 km grid resolution, and the second where the bathymetry from the ETOPO5 data set (Data announcement 88-MGG-02, Digital relief of the Surface of the Earth, NOAA, National Geophysical Data Center, Boulder, Colorado, 1988) are interpolated into 4 km grid resolution. See Table 2.

Experiment	Bottom	Storm
RUN1	ETOPO5	No
RUN2	20 km	No
RUN3	ETOPO5	Yes
RUN4	20 km	Yes

Table 2: Experiments in this paper.

3 Model results -no atmospheric pressure

The bottom topography from the ETOPO5 data set (RUN1), gives generally an increase in the speed at the end of the simulations (7 to 10 days), see Figure 4 and 5 a) - c). For the deepest location (OL4 Figure 4 and 5 d)) the speed is significant larger trough out the whole simulation period for RUN1. There has been an important topographic change at OL4 for the two simulations. In RUN1 OL4 is located at the bottom of a steep wall at one side and a slope on the other side, see Figure 2 a) . In RUN2 OL4 lies in a slope. It is therefore probable that this is an effect from focusing of the currents.

OL5 is the location that has experienced least topographic changes between RUN1 and RUN2. The result is that for OL5 the plots are more alike than for the other stations both in amplitude and in period. One exception is in RUN2 (Figure 4 e)), OL5 has a significant peak in the speed at approximately 4 days. This peak is not present in RUN1.

The oscillations seem to be more harmonic and stable for RUN1 than for RUN2. See for instance Figure 6 b), 8 c) or 10 b). This can be due to waves generated from the topography.

From the velocity components in x - and y - direction the oscillations have a shorter period in RUN1. The amplitude of the oscillations for RUN1, will also be increased at the shallower sections (OL1 and OL2). At OL1 the mean flow is directed north-east. For deeper sections (OL3, OL4 and OL5) the mean flow is directed toward the coast, south, south-east.

At OL1 there are an increase in both temperature and salinity. The increase is strongest for RUN1, Figure 12 and 14 a). The amplitudes of the oscillations are also significant larger and more periodic for RUN1 than RUN2 at OL2, Figure 12 and 14 b). The temperature oscillates approximately with 2 degrees in RUN1 at OL2. For the deeper locations there are a decrease in temperature and salinity. Again the decrease is strongest for RUN1 indicating that the climatological data is too smooth. The isotherms are therefore steepened by the thermohaline circulation. Since the temperature and salinity at OL2 oscillates around the initial value, the shelf break is approximately at the center of the steepening process of the isotherms.

4 Model result with travelling low pressure

The speed Figures 16 and 17 show that the speed decay more rapid for RUN3 compared to RUN4. This indicate that rough bottom extract more energy and therefore damps oscillations sooner than a smooth bottom.

From the velocity in x - and y -direction, see for instance Figure 18 or 20 not only the damping of the oscillations in RUN3 is striking, but also that the oscillations drifts out of phase. The result is that the oscillations in RUN3 have shorter period than oscillations in RUN4. Usually the difference is between 1 and 5 hours shorter dependent on which velocity component, salinity or temperature that are considered. Since the kinetic energy goes as $U^2 + V^2$, the non linearity can maybe explain the shift in period.

At OL5 there are smaller changes in amplitude and period than for the other locations in RUN3 and RUN4i, see Figure 19, 23 or 27 e). The reason may be that the local bottom topography at OL5 is less modified than at OL1-OL4. See Figure 2.

Comparing the velocity in y -direction, Figure 20 d) and 21 d), the maximum peaks of the oscillations are more disturbed 50 m above sea bed.

For the velocity in the z -direction the downwelling at OL1 (Figure 22 a)) at approximately 3 days are much stronger when the ETOPO5 bottom topography is used. OL1 is 80 m shallower located in RUN3 than in RUN4.

So in that sense higher vertical speed can be expected. The effect of stronger down flow at OL1 can be seen in the salinity and the temperature plot. Warm and salt water is displaced downward, which increases the salinity and temperature at OL1. For deeper sections there will be an decrease in temperature and salinity.

5 Discussion

When the driving forces are the thermohaline circulation and the tide, the model produces maximum currents less than 0.2 m/s 10 m above sea bed and 0.25 m/s 50 m above sea bed. The mean currents are directed north-east for the upper layer and south, south east for deeper layers. Bottom topography from the ETOPO5 dataset gives oscillations with periods at approximately 24 hours. The periods are longer when bottom interpolated from the 20 km model is being used. For salinity and temperature an increase in the upper and decrease in the deeper sections are found. This is probably caused by too weak thermohaline field. The strongest increase and decrease was produced for simulations with bottom topography from the ETOPO5 data.

For simulations where the driving forces also included travelling low pressure systems, the model produced maximum currents that was very dependent on the depth. 10 m above sea bed the maximum currents were approximately 0.7 m/s for OL1, 0.35 m/s for OL2 and less then 0.3 m/s for the deeper locations. Equal features were found 50 m above sea bed with maximum speed a bit higher. Approximately 0.9 m/s at OL1, 0.5 m/s at OL2 and less than 0.35 m/s for the deeper locations. For the simulations where atmospheric lows entered the area, the ETOPO5 bottom data gave a strong damping of the oscillations that occurred. This indicate that rougher bottom extracts energy faster than smooth bottom. The mean transport in the deeper layer remains south, south-east. Also for this simulation there are an increase in temperature and salinity for the shallowest station and a decrease for the deeper stations. The oscillations from the simulations with bottom from the ETOPO5 dataset and bottom from the 20 km model drifts out of phase since the ETOPO5 bottom topography gives shorter periods then the other.

OL5 stands out with least variations in the four simulations. There are peak events in speed that do not correspond in the two comparable simulations, but when looking at the velocity components we see that it is the amplitude that is not captured well. OL5 is the location that has experienced least topographic changes between the ETOPO5 and the 20 km models.

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Speed

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 4: Time series of speed OL1-OL5, 10 m above the sea bed. Solid line 4 km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 5: Time series of speed OL1-OL5, 50 m above the sea bed. Solid line 4 km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

Velocity in x -direction

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 6: Time series of velocity in x -direction OL1-OL5, 10m above the sea bed. Solid line 4 km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 7: Time series of velocity in x -direction OL1-OL5, 50m above the sea bed. Solid line 4 km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

Velocity in y -direction

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 8: Time series of velocity in y -direction OL1-OL5, 10m above the sea bed. Solid line 4 km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 9: Time series of velocity in y -direction OL1-OL5, 50 m above the sea bed. Solid line 4 km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

Velocity in z -direction

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 10: Time series of velocity in z -direction OL1-OL5, 10 m above the sea bed. Solid line 4 km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 11: Time series of velocity in z -direction OL1-OL5, 50 m above the sea bed. Solid line 4 km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

Salinity

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 12: Time series of salinity OL1-OL5, 10 m above the sea bed. Solid line 4 km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 13: Time series of salinity OL1-OL5, 50 m above the sea bed. Solid line 4 km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

Temperature

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 14: Time series of temperature OL1-OL5, 10m above the sea bed. Solid line 4km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 15: Time series of temperature OL1-OL5, 50 m above the sea bed. Solid line 4 km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

Speed

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 16: Time series of speed OL1-OL5, 10 m above the sea bed. Solid line 4 km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 17: Time series of speed OL1-OL5, 50 m above the sea bed. Solid line 4 km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

Velocity in x -direction

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 18: Time series of velocity in x -direction OL1-OL5, 10 m above the sea bed. Solid line 4 km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 19: Time series of velocity in x -direction OL1-OL5, 50 m above the sea bed. Solid line 4 km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

Velocity in y -direction

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 20: Time series of velocity in y -direction OL1-OL5, 10 m above the sea bed. Solid line 4 km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 21: Time series of velocity in y -direction OL1-OL5, 50 m above the sea bed. Solid line 4 km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

Velocity in z -direction

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 22: Time series of velocity in z -direction OL1-OL5, 10 m above the sea bed. Solid line 4 km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 23: Time series of velocity in z -direction OL1-OL5, 50 m above the sea bed. Solid line 4 km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

Salinity

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 24: Time series of salinity OL1-OL5, 10 m above the sea bed. Solid line 4 km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 25: Time series of salinity OL1-OL5, 50 m above the sea bed. Solid line 4 km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

Temperature

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 26: Time series of temperature OL1-OL5, 10m above the sea bed. Solid line 4km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

(a) OL1

(b) OL2

(c) OL3

(d) OL4

(e) OL5

Figure 27: Time series of temperature OL1-OL5, 50 m above the sea bed. Solid line 4 km (ETOPO5) and dotted line 4 km interpolated from 20 km grid resolution.

References

- [1] J. Berntsen. USERS GUIDE for a modesplit σ -coordinate numerical ocean model. Technical Report 135, Dept. of Applied Mathematics, University of Bergen, Johs. Bruns gt.12, N-5008 Bergen, Norway, 2000. 48p.
- [2] T. Eldevik, I. Eliassen, J. Berntsen, and G. Furnes. On the influence of the thermohaline circulation at Ormen Lange. Technical report, Dept. of Applied Mathematics, University of Bergen, Johs. Bruns gt.12, N-5008 Bergen, Norway, 2001. 29p.
- [3] I. Eliassen, T. Eldevik, J. Berntsen, and G. Furnes. The current conditions at Ormen Lange - Storegga. Technical report, Dept. of Applied Mathematics, University of Bergen, Johs. Bruns gt.12, N-5008 Bergen, Norway, 2000. 22p.
- [4] D.R. Lynch, J.T.C. Ip, C.E. Naimie, and F.E. Werner. Convergence studies of tidally-rectified circulation on Georges Bank. In D.R. Lynch and A.M. Davies, editors, *Quantitative Skill Assessment for Coastal Ocean Models*. American Geophysical Union, 1995.
- [5] E.A. Martinsen and H. Engedahl. Implementation and testing of a lateral boundary scheme as an open boundary condition in a barotropic ocean model. *Coastal Engineering*, 11:603–627, 1987.
- [6] E.A. Martinsen, B. Gjevik, and L.P. Røed. A numerical model for long barotropic waves and storm surges along the western coast of Norway. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, 9:1126–1138, 1979.
- [7] Ø. Thiem, T. Eldevik, and J. Berntsen. Combined effects of thermohaline and atmosphere forcing on the currents at Ormen Lange. Technical Report 150, Department of Mathematics, University of Bergen, Norway, 2001.
- [8] F. Vikebø, J. Berntsen, and G. Furnes. Analysis of events at Ormen Lange: measurements and modelling. Technical report, Dept. of Applied Mathematics, University of Bergen, Johs. Bruns gt.12, N-5008 Bergen, Norway, 2001.
- [9] F. Vikebø, J. Berntsen, and G. Furnes. Numerical studies of the response of currents at Ormen Lange to travelling storms. Technical report, Dept. of Applied Mathematics, University of Bergen, Johs. Bruns gt.12, N-5008 Bergen, Norway, 2001.